

THE PROCESS OF IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS THROUGH UZBEK FOLK SONGS

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Abstract: This article presents an analysis of the processes of using Uzbek folk songs in improving the professional training of future teachers.

Key words: folk, song, preparation, professional, pedagogical, process, factors, component, emotional, volitional.

The topic "The problem of improving the professional thinking of a future music teacher" included a number of tasks:

- ❖ professional activation of students' personal valuable attitude to professional activity;
- ❖ to inform them about the purpose and activities of music art and music pedagogy, the importance of Uzbek folk songs in the life of society, and the factors that determine the importance of musical and pedagogical activities;
- ❖ reveal knowledge about conflicts in positions regarding professional music pedagogy.

Even today, it is focused on the fact that the point of view on this problem has changed in different periods of the development of society. If even in the past decades, for example, in our country, the position on this issue took an important place, even now, music is a powerful tool for training certain moral virtues of a person (philosophy, humanitarianism, philosophical, spiritual, pedagogical, educational and other). In recent years, there has been a position that music creates favorable aesthetic and psychological conditions for not only personal development, but also moral, national, and professional development. It does not directly affect specific national, moral and personal qualities, but affects it as a mechanism of "emotional-volitional" practical activity of education. As an example, we can cite the "State Anthem of the Republic of Uzbekistan". Perhaps, the clash of two different positions is controversial, any analysis of a specific problem, debate, defense of one's own position, and first of all, from the point of view of analyzing the problem itself, the unique characteristics of the field of music pedagogy, strategic, prospective plans are precisely by the students. mastery is achieved. In this process, future music teachers become bold and persistent in their professional training, striving to improve their position on this or that problem.

Future music teachers in the process of improving their professional training through Uzbek folk songs form initial ideas about their personal and professional qualities, reflect the essence of this important aspect of their professional training. During the musical-theoretical lessons, it is necessary to determine how the students understood the meaning and difference of concepts such as "Uzbek folk songs", "pedagogical methodology" and "music pedagogic methodology", "music teaching methodology", its content, types, forms, genres. Reflecting on these issues, students do this based on their experiences of musical pedagogy and philosophical, general professional, scientific training, in particular, ideas about categories and laws. Here they "go" to discover general professional knowledge in various scientific and

musical fields. Continuing the conversation that began in the lecture about the professional levels of perception and implementation of professional problems, future music teachers, with the help of the teacher, present examples of such approaches using the literature proposed by them, knowledge of the methodology of music education, and practical experience in general secondary schools. due to the complexity of the concept, it repeatedly and deeply discusses its essence. At the same time, it is important to refer to each student, to set the task of connecting the presented theoretical model with a real reflection in the personality of each of them.

Interest in the problem of a professional-creative approach to music education, and this approach consists in improving not only the purpose of the student, but also professional knowledge, abilities and competencies, in the integrity of the didactic and pedagogical process. During classroom training, it is important to make students aware of the most important sign of the manifestation of methodological professional culture - the existence of career-oriented didactic education. Relying on the literature, it is necessary to force students to independently identify different aspects of this thinking - from a scientific and professional-creative point of view. Instills in students a desire to analyze and self-assess their emerging style of professional knowledge. Students directly directed their practical and creative energies to the use of methodological analysis to solve problems of professional importance. Based on them, the personal and valuable attitude to the educational institution, musical-pedagogical process deepened, and the desire to improve various aspects of professional activity was manifested. The process of developing the content and operational components of the professional training of future music teachers during training sessions was carried out indirectly (observing music lessons, preparing students to conduct them) and in direct contact with students when performing special instructions and tasks of a creative nature. In order to involve them in methodological analysis and thus to identify possible practical ways of solving these conflicts, in some cases, in order to develop methods of their creative use professional activities and experience students, students conduct self-analysis in classes with students of general secondary schools and on this basis their Efforts were made to build a promising program for the development of personal and professional qualities. Thus, in the course of the conducted professional analysis, future music teachers had the opportunity to creatively apply all the professional knowledge, skills, skills and competence methods learned during theoretical and practical training.

Important aspects of methodological analysis are the specific features and principles of its implementation, including the role and essence of the principle of objective and subjective relations. Another important principle for our research is the principle of career orientation. Its essence has been discussed before. It is up to the students to demonstrate the application of this principle themselves. The basis for this can be a methodological analysis of one of the previously performed problems of music pedagogy. Here, didactic relations such as "prescribing from above", "unlimited guardianship of the student", "strict regulation of the style of educational activities", "accuracy of the presented material", "importance of folk songs in professional training", "performance positions by students" of the types of lessons need to be regulated. The pedagogical, psychological and moral side of the musical pedagogical process should also be significantly changed when conducting lessons: "student" - "teacher", that is, it should be moved to an active, effective, dialectical, interactive process of "two sides". Respect for each other, separation in order to come to the rescue is not the desired goal, but

the norm of this process should be the adoption of new positions achieved and personally accepted by each participant.

With more experience, he can help students independently fulfill the most important requirement of the principle of professional guidance - to analyze specific problems based on a deep understanding of the laws of music and pedagogy. Of course, the teacher should do everything in his power so that the students themselves actively participate in this creative process. In the professional analysis of a specific problem of music pedagogy, it is appropriate to show the cases where the students themselves came to "discoveries" and used them in their practical work in the general secondary school.

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